

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B0084
Date: 09 Feb 2005
Take Off: 10:30:38
Landing: 15:45:40
Flight Time: 5h15m02

Trials Instructions: AUTEX – Pennines Rotor Experiment:
Operating Area: Over the Pennines and the Vale of York.

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Graham Morgan	BAe Systems
3	Mission Scientist 1	Dave Kindred	Met Office
4	Flight Manager	John Reid	FAAM
5	Flight Manager (training)	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	Mission Scientist (training)	Dave Pollard	Met Office
8	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
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Flight Track:

B084 Track 09-FEB-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b084
 Date: 9th Feb 2005
 Project: Lee Waves
 Location: Pennines and Vale of York

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
092435		Start posn	0.00 kft	106	52'04.36N 0'37.48W
101901		INU to NAV	0.02 kft	106	
102406		Taxy	0.02 kft	106	
103038		Take Off			Cranfield
103847		Video	10.0 kft	347	Start recording FWD + DWN
110714	112317	Run 1	4.0 kft	254	
113144	114158	Run 2.1	5.0 kft	076	
114519	115120	Run 2.2	5.0 kft	173	
115506	121029	Run 2.3	6.0 kft	256	
121519	122537	Run 3.1	8.0 kft	070	
121622		Dropsonde 1 launch	8.0 kft	074	
122847	123427	Run 3.2	8.0 kft	333	
123516	124917	Run 3.3	8.0 kft	281	
125343	130253	Run 4.1	9.0 kft	073	
125443		Dropsonde 2 launch	9.0 kft	090	
130907	131305	Run 4.2	9.0 kft	175	
131750	132428	Run 5.1	6.1 - 6.0 kft	323	
132741	133349	Run 5.2	5.0 kft	141	
133800		Video			Change tapes
133801	134513	Run 5.3	4.0 kft	298	
134853	135520	Run 5.4	3.0 kft	164	
135926	140623	Run 5.5	2.2 kft	310	
142552	144116	Run 6.1	9.0 kft	256	
143827		Dropsonde 3 launch	9.0 kft	258	
144936		DS 4 launch	9.0 kft	088	
144936	145826	Run 6.2	9.0 - 7.1 kft	093	FM PC crashed at end of Run
150531	151645	Profile 1	0.2 - 11.0 kft	162	
154540		Land			Cranfield
155136		Stop GPS pos	0.07 kft	307	52'04.36N 0'37.48W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B084 Track 09-FEB-05

FAAM Sortie Brief

Pennines Rotor Experiment:

Flight No: B084

Date: 09/02/2005

Trial objectives:

To investigate the structure of lee waves and associated rotors across and downwind of the Pennines. The flight will consist of a series of stacked SLRs between points A and D from MPA to FL100.

Location:

Over the Pennines and the Vale of York.

Leeming airfield = 1°33'W, 54°18' N

Linton on Ouse airfield = 1°15' W, 54°02' N

Point A = point to the west of Linton at 1°25'W, 54°10'N

Point B = point to the west of the Pennines upwind from point A at 2°45'W 54°00'N

Point C = point to the west of the Pennines upwind from point D at 3°00'W 54°25'N

Point D = point to the north of Leeming at 1°45'W, 54°30'N

Weather:

General strong westerly flow across the Pennines, warm sector, stable airflow preferred.

Flight pattern:

1. [1030] Take off from Cranfield airport Transit to point A at convenient altitude aiming to arrive at point A at FL040 (30 mins).
2. Perform a SLR from point A into wind to point B (20 mins)
3. Reposition to point C climbing to FL050 (10 mins)
4. Perform SLRs C-D and D-A at FL050 (25 mins)
5. Climb in turn to FL060 and perform a SLR A-B (20 mins)
6. Turn and climb at point B to FL070 (5 mins)
7. Perform SLR B-A at FL070 dropping one sonde at point B (20 mins)
8. Turn and climb to FL080 and SLRs A-D & D-C at FL080. (25 mins)
9. Turn and climb to FL090 and fly SLR C-D & D-A dropping one sonde at point C (25 mins)
10. Descend to FL060 (5 mins)
11. Fly series of SLRs between A and D at FL060, FL050, FL040, FL030, FL020, FL010 (60 mins)
12. If time permits, climb to FL060 at point A (5 mins)
13. Perform a SLR from point A-B (20 mins)
14. Reposition to point C descending to FL050 (10 mins)
15. Perform SLRs C-D and D-A at FL050 (25 mins)
16. Recover to Cranfield (30 mins)

Total sortie time 335

N.B.

- All Flight Level changes to be undertaken at approximately 1000ft/min
- All heights are relative to 1013 hPa

INCLUDE:

1. An assessment of the flight.
2. Summary of the weather conditions.

Overall a v. successful sortie to investigate structure of low waves and associated rotors across & downwind of N. Pennines.

After T/O Cranfield 1030z, we transitioned at FL 100 to point A, descending to FLO40 to begin Run 1 at 1107. A series of S&L runs, following an open-ended, flat 'horseshoe' pattern described by A, B, C, D as above ensued, runs 1 to Run 4.2, ending 1313z. Dropsondes ejected at 1216 (near point B) and at 1254 (near point C), both giving 'good' P, T, U, and 'good' winds on sonde 2.

Next, a series of runs along the Vale of York A → D, D → A etc were flown at FL 060, FLO50, FLO40, FLO30 and FL 022 (lowest allowed by ATC), runs 5.1 → 5.5, 1317 → 1406.

Thereafter, a climb towards point A was made, to FLO90, and a further "sideways horseshoe" flown A → B (Run 6) with dropsonde ejected near B at 1438, 146.2, C → D, with dropsonde ejected near C at 1449 (both 'good' P, T, U and wind data), finishing Run 6.2 at FLO70 (ATC avoidance), 1425 → 1458.

Finally, a missed approach (to 200') over KEETING runway was made (150531) climbing out at 1000'/min SSEwards towards Cranfield, up to FL110. (end 1516)

A recovery to Cranfield was made, landing at 1545Z
(Sertie time Sh 15m).

All instrumentation appeared to work well, except a 'lock-up'
on the Flight Managers HERACE PC, 1459Z for N Sumis, but
soon recovered - no incoming HERACE data was lost, and other
PC's displaying HERACE stayed 'up'. Some icing noted on FFC
from time to time.

Light → Moderate wave activity noticed, both in the cloud formations
seen (significant Ac len + Ac/As/Ci/Cs layers to EAST of
line (A) → (D), whereas only Ci/Cs to WEST of this Vale of York
line) and in the T/Td and 'w' (vert vel Z) waves noted
along runs - typically about 4 minute wavelength period.

Cloud conditions overall were generally 6-8/8 Cu/Sc, base ~3000'
tops up to 7000', with mostly clear skies above over sideways
horseshoe runs (out isolated Ac len & thickening Ci/Cs seen ^{in west} during
flight) ~~in west~~. Wave-clouds seen to E. of line (A) → (D).
(Several digital camera photos taken). Murky, misty conditions under Cu/Sc.

Winds generally 250° → 280°, little directional shear
in vertical, slowly increasing with height ~30 kt at 5000'
and ~50 kt at 9000'.

Some ppt (water ^{mainly} drops) encountered in & below thicker Cu/Sc,
although ATC icing noted on F1060 run(s).

An interesting sertie to fly, which should yield a
v. useful dataset, especially when combined with other ground-based
measurements being taken by Swiss Vesper's group (notably Sende data).

NOTE: Preliminary & significant
Time spent with aircrew detailing the EXACT location of
ground position, ^{(A) → (D)} flown over, liaison with ATC (Vale of York was
very busy with other Air Traffic) before & during sertie etc was
very worthwhile and no doubt contributed to the smooth running
and success of the mission.

DEC, 10/2/05.

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.084**

 Date **9-2-05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					1024 QNH.
1024					Start Taxi from Cranfield. EGTC
1030			→		T/O Cranfield. 1- ³ / ₈ Sc ⁷ / ₈ Sc/Ac/As above.
1031					(th) Sc base ~ 1200-1300'. Tops 2000'.
1033	TRANSIT	Passing 4500'	350°	-	Transit to point A on sortie brief. (Gottesmore later) SW of Cranfield
1039	"	leveling FL000	347°	S2.2W 0.8W	Wind 280/15 m/sec { ⁵ / ₈ Sc/ST below ⁷ / ₈ Ci/Cs/As above
1058	"	Descending before starting			Wind 1. to FL060
1059	"	FL050	338°	S3.9W 1.0W	{ ⁵ / ₈ Sc/ST below ⁶ / ₈ Ci/Ac/As above
1103		leveling	→		prepare to start 1 st leg. Cloud tops up to 4000'
1104					Generally ³ / ₈ Sc/ST below - good ops Generally clear ahead - good evidence of lenticular Ac above
1105	Wind check				(^{ATC} 260/40kt 262/18 m/sec Horse (1/8) But ⁶ / ₈ upper cloud behind (to E) Ac/As/Cs
110714	R1	FL040	256°	S4.1N 1.4W	Start Run 1. (A) → (B) at FL040
110855		into cloud now			81T turbulence. 1013 QNH BRENSLEY. Local
111300		Still in cloud			(In cloud for most of run)
111635		into clearer air now			(between layers) Some convective elements around.
111650		Back into cloud now.			
		[T & Td have			On this leg no clear sign of relative changes in vertical electric field nil sig waves shown on HORSE
111855		into clearer air now			⁷ / ₈ Sc below (w tops ~ 3000', occ 4000' ahead)
112317	R1	7.1kft	→	S4.0 2.7W	End R1 (climb to FL050 & head towards point C)

* R/T better to use than Intercom ✓
(Louder, clearer & to "ALL" Scientists)

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.084**

 Date **9-2-05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1126					Positioning toward pt (C) at FLO50
					6/8 Cu Sc below (generally tops up to 3500' but 5000') 7/8 Ac/As/Cs above.
113144	START R2.1	5.0kft	080°	54.4N 2.9W	Start Run 2.1 (C) → (D)
1133		→			In east of Cu tops this end of run. 8ft turbulence
1136					Generally just at Cu tops, but clear above ahead good evidence of Ac lenticularis ahead.
113910		In cloud now.			
114140		Clear now			Waves above (Mainly Ac lens)
114158	END R2.1	5.0kft	083	54.5N 1.7W	End R2.1. 4/8 Cu Sc below (good cloud break below us at (D)) Turning ↗ onto next run at FLO50
114519	START R2.2	5.0kft	171°	54.4N 1.7W	Start R2.2 (D) → (A) (D) → (A)
					Into cu tops/Sc at start of run.
		In east of cloud along			this leg; some light ^{at} this end of run.
115120	END R2.2	4.9kft	158°	54.1N 1.4W	End R2.2. Turn ↗ & climb to FLO60
		In cloud on			most of turn.
115506	START R2.3	6.0kft	258°	54.1N 1.4W	Start R2.3
115620		→			Into clear air now 6/8 Cu/Sc below Clear above except 1/8 thin Ci ahead & some contrails to SW.
115725		→			In tops of Cu now.
115820		→			Skimming Cu tops now at FLO60
120230		→			Still in cloud, some icing here.
120340		Some turbulence here			(Front cockpit window, ice detector FPC frozen in picture, wing light on)
		Significant power changes on this run (wave activity)			
					+ 5m/sec amp ↑ period/wavelength 0.2° long.

Same wave activity in T & Tq (n4min wavelength)

Vert. vel.
 LITTLE T/Td wave activity

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.084**.....

Date **9-2-05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121029	R2.3	FLO60	255	54.0N 2.8W	End R2.3 at point (B) Climb & turn onto reciprocal for next run (B) → (A) at FLO80 & drop side within 1 min of start of run. (check to (B))
121519	START 3.1	FLO80	080	53.9N 2.6W	Start R3.1
121622	"	FLO80	"	54.0 2.6W	Drop side Release Hand #1. 7/8 Cu Sc below (tops ~ 6000') over top (Azlen) Waves clouds above & well ahead. Wind 270/42 271/23 m/sec (Front/CAPT) (Helix)
121928		into cloud for few secs			(121) (to top) Great Temp/Humid Air; Winds not good (damage GPS antenna?)
122500					6/8 Cu/Sc below CLEAR 4/8 Az Cas turbulent ahead
122637	END R3.1	FLO80	082	54.1N 1.3W	Turning for next leg A → D at FLO80
122847	START R3.2	FLO80	333	54.1N 1.4W	Start R3.2 7/8 Cu Sc below Waves to E over Az len above here
123427	END R3.2	FLO80	317	54.4N 1.6W	End R3.2 * Missing GPR (ATC CONF) so will turn onto track towards pt (C). clear Temp/humid air previously
123516	START R3.3	FLO80	281	54.4 1.7W	Start R3.3 heading for point (C). [TRIED TO CALL KRETER - NO RESPONSE - TRY LATER (GPS PLANNED)]
124917	3.3	FLO80	264	54.4N 3.0W	Turn declimb for FLO80 (leg (A)-(B)) Surging in ATC power as turning at this W. end. (No cloud waves) Cloud: 7/8 Cu Sc below (tops ~ 7000') Thicker Ci/Cs/As at W. end but clear ahead. (to E)
125130					

* Vert wind as per 2.3 in latter (days); 2.5W small over T/O 21.0

Wave activity still seen but less

have Jim in

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.084**.....

Date **9-2-05**.....

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Same West vol - wave activity - less marked - Temp structure

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125343	R4.1	8.9 kft	090°	54.4N 2.7W	Start R4. ① → ②
125443	→	9.0 kft	088°	54.4N 2.7W	Dropsonde #2 is Dropped.
1256			→		Good Met & Winds data from sondes
1258					7/8 Cu Sc below, new clear above. Act len / Ci / Cs ahead.
130253	END R4.1	9.0	-	54.4N 1.5W	END R4.1 at ③, descend to FLO60 for ATC
					Manoeuvring to get back to FLO60 & perform run 4.2 ④ → ⑤ (probably // run)
130907	START R4.2	9.0 kft	167	54.4N 1.5W	Start R4.2. Hdg for pt ④, slightly diff track (start ~ 2 wds E of original point ④ but crossing → pt ④ at end of run)
131255			→		[Bit turn now to avoid traffic]
131305	END R4.2	9.0 kft	166	54.4N 1.4W	End R4.2. Descend to FLO60
					START NEXT SECTION OF SORTIE NOW =
					VALUE OF TRACK { ④ → ⑤ - ④ WIND AT VARIOUS ALTS } *
131516			→		Into cloud at ~ FLO70.
131645					Out of cloud now
131750	START R5.1	6.0 kft	323°	54.2N 1.4W	START R5.1 at FLO60 ④ → ⑤
					In East of Cu/Sc tops at this height (mostly east)
					7/8 Cu/Sc below; generally clear above 1/8 Ci Wave clouds to E.
					FF camera should give good idea of cloud tops.
132428	END R5.1	6.0 kft	326°	54.5N 1.7W	END R5.1. Manoeuvre & descend
132741	START R5.2	5.0 kft	141°	54.5N 1.7W	START R5.2 ⑥ → ⑦.
132840					In ^{thick} cloud on this run
			Wind check		Wind 258/18 m/sec 253/27kt
133349	END R5.2	5.0 kft	150°	54.1N 1.4W	END R5.2 Descend to FLO40
					C. Base ~ 2500 - 3000' ? (at 1/8 level)

Some clear patches below

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.084**.....

Date **9-2-05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
133806	Start R5.3	4.0kft	304°	54.1N 1.4W	Start R5.3 at 12040
1339			→		Mainly in cloud, but generally clear below
1342			318°	→	Starting to rain now on this leg. thicker cloud here is approaching
134505					Still in thicker cloud
134513	End R5.3	4.0kft	325°	54.5N 1.7W	End R5.3. Descend to FLO35 to view cloud & turn
					Can see ground OK at this min alt.
134853	Start R5.4	3.0kft	164°	54.1N 1.7W	So descend to FLO30. Start R5.4.
1350			→		Raining. Near cloud base here mostly underneath.
1354					C. base ~ 500' - 1000' higher this end of run.
135520	End R5.4	3.0kft	165°	54.1N 1.3W	End R5.4
135602			→		O/h AT/N on IFC. For
135728			→		check
					Descend to 2200' for R5.5.
135926	Start R5.5	2.2kft	313°	54.1N 1.4W	Start R5.5
140140					Under Cu/Sc base but still rain here.
					Cloud base lower on N. end of run.
140623	End R5.5	2.2kft	319°	54.1N 1.7W	End R5.5. Turning ↓ & try to stay at 2.2kft if get ATC permission
					Cannot do lowest run at FLO10 or FLO12 & " do LEGALLY MISSED APPROACH now (too much traffic)
					So head for point (A), FLO60 & perform horsehoe pattern.
1417					Clear cloud now at 6.0kft
					Climb to FLO90, head for (A)
					to do race track (A) → (B), and drop at (B)

(C) → (D) " " " (E) } FL 02

Mission Scientist's Log

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Date **9-2-05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
142550	R6.1	9.0kft	260°	54.1W 1.4W	Start R6. (A) → (B) 7/8 Cu Sc below 5/8 Ci Above
1434			→		7/8 Cu Sc below - Ci/Cs/As thickening ahead
143827	R6.1	9.0kft	258°	54.0W 2.5W	Wind comp. → Wind 257/24m/sec / 267/51 kt. DOP S/W #3 released.
144116	R6.1	9.0kft	259°	54.0W 2.7W	Winds + Temp ^{GOOD DATA} ✓ End R6.1. Upper Cloud thicker here. (solid? ppt falling from above)
					Head to point (C) for next run & dropwind
144936	START R6.2	9.0kft	085°	54.4W 2.6W	Start R6.2 / + S/W #4 released
1453			→		7/8 Cu Sc below 1/8 Ci / Cs above behind (D)
145635			→		& Some wave activity well ahead (to E) Hardly to descend to FLO70 (traffic avoidance) on this run. (descend @ 1000'/min)
145826	END R6.2	7.0kft	087°	54.4W 1.7W	END R6.2 APPROACH (MISSED) into LEEMING; ALERT
1459			→		HORACE PROBLEM F/Man. trying to recover. (A/Sc HORACE on LAPTOP OK). Problem with F/Man ^{PC} displaying loaded. ; data coming in OK.
150531	START P1	200'	167°	54.2W 1.5W	200' o/h LEEMING RUNWAY. Start P1 at 1000'/min heading SSE climbing out of area
1512	P1				Cu/Sc cloud tops ~ 6,500 ft. Flying along boundary 6/8 wavecloud to BEST (E) ; 7/8 Ci to STBD (W) Ac/As
151645	END P1	FL010	170°	53.5W 1.1W	End P1 ; END SCIENCE, RTB (Cairfield)
1546:15					Land Fuel at shutdown.

Good wave activity west of T
 similar to run 5 in period
 Start run → 20W
 Main wave
 Similar (but less pronounced) on T/E

L.	Cen.	R.
1050	0	1150

Flight B084 Dropsonde Landing Positions 09th February 2005

Sonde 1	54.02376 N	2.55935 W
Sonde 2	54.42922 N	2.75576 W
Sonde 3	54.04159 N	2.43879 W
Sonde 4	54.44046 N	2.92091 W

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B084**

Date: 09/02/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP		N
Satcom C		Y	PCASP		N
Satcom H		Y	2D-P		N
			2D-C		N
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	Y	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1		N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann		Y	CPI	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			HVPS	N	
G. Eastern		Y	Racks:		
J. Williams		Y	INC	N	
Nevzorov		Y	CCN / CNC	Y	N
TWC		Y	CVI	Y	
FWVS		N			
<u>Radiometers</u>			<u>Aerosol</u>		
Upper Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	Y	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	N
Lower Clear	Y	Y			
“ Red	Y	Y			
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N				
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS		N			
MARSS		N			
DEIMOS		N			
ARIES		N			
SWS		N			
<u>Chemistry</u>					
Ozone		N			
ECGC	N				
NOX		N			
CO		N	<u>Others:</u>		
ORAC	Y	N	NIR TDLAS		N
PAN	Y	N	2BT O3		N
PERCA	Y	N	VACC		N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B084

Date: 09/02/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC is dark compared to other cameras on core console displays.
2. FFC iced-up twice during flight, both at FL60 –3.24 degrees
3. FM PC locked up, perhaps coincident with the end of a run. Switched off/on to recover.

Aircraft

Infrared 09 Feb 2005 0800 UTC

 Forecast chart (T+12)
Valid 1200 UTC Wed 09 Feb 2005

Temperatures and precipitation

Wind speed and direction at 10 m

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B084:

Log	Reason

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	3 Oct 2006	Doug Anderson	There are no missing logs for this flight
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Rear/Downward Facing Cameras

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Jonathan P. Taylor

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